

Development and validation of a photo-based attitudes scale towards the conservation of semi-arid habitats

Francisco López-de-Haro¹, María Martínez-Chico² (ORCID: 0000-0002-6219-7107), Fabián Martínez-Hernández³ * (corresponding author) (ORCID: 0000-0002-5124-5492), Javier López-Tomás⁴, Juan Francisco Mota Poveda³ (ORCID: 0000-0001-5754-279X)

¹ **University of Almería, RNM-344, 04120, Almería, Spain**

² **University of Almería, 04120, Almería, Spain**

³ **University of Almería, CECOUAL, RNM-344, 04120, Almería, Spain**

⁴ **Barcelona, Spain**

*** corresponding author: Fabián Martínez-Hernández (ORCID: 0000-0002-5124-5492) e-mail address: fmh177@ual.es; telephone number: +34 620534056**

Abstract

The biodiversity crisis is one of the most pressing problems of our time. Arid and semi-arid environments are the refuge of a very important part of global biodiversity, they provide essential ecosystem services and are extremely fragile, which makes their protection necessary. However, these habitats are often undervalued and even generate rejection among the population, which creates problems for their conservation. This all entails the need to implement educational and awareness strategies in regards to this issue. To this end, a project was undertaken with secondary school students in the southeast of Spain, the driest territory in Europe. In this work we focus on the development and validation of an instrument designed to evaluate the instructional effectiveness carried out to improve attitude towards drylands. It is a scale of attitudes based on photos, an innovative instrument that poses a Likert-type questionnaire referring to each one of the habitats under consideration, whose development involved 490 participants. The standardization criteria established to select the photos and the criteria/attributes on which to base the wording of the questionnaire items were two of the basic pillars of this methodological proposal. Its psychometric properties support its validity and reliability to a sufficient degree to be used in educational research projects with students aged 13 to 16 in these types of semi-arid habitats. However, indications are provided showing that the scale could be applied to other ages and habitats, even on an international scale, given the extent of arid zones around the world.

Keywords

Biodiversity, conservation, Environmental education, landscape.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most used and cited approaches for explaining landscape preferences and perception of environment is the “Habitat theory” (Orians 1980). According to this approach, the perception and aesthetic evaluation people have of a specific landscape depend on the characteristics appreciated therein that favor survival itself (Appleton 1996) and are related, therefore, to an evolutionary adaptation (Bernáldez 1981; Appleton 1996; Falk and Balling 2010). Likewise, attention has been drawn to the preference for places with surface water presence (Ulrich 1981; Kaplan and Kaplan 1989; Arriaza et al. 2004) and abundant vegetation (Joye and Van den Berg 2011), phenomena that Bernáldez (1985) referred to as hydrophilia and phytophilia, respectively. The term biophilia (Wilson 1984), in reference to “love” for life in general, has been more widely used. Seemingly deprived of these characteristics, it is unsurprising that arid and semi-arid environments are habitually undervalued and even rejected by the population (Mota et al. 2004; García-Llorente et al. 2012; Mendoza-Fernández et al. 2014; Gil de Araujo 2019), regardless if they are protected areas (DeLucio and Múgica 1994). This assessment may, however, depend on many factors, such as socio-economic status, place of residence or culture of origin (Andrade et al. 2019). Furthermore, a large proportion of citizens see the conservation of natural spaces as a limitation to the development of agriculture and tourism, which drive the economy in the south east of Spain, where this study was carried out (Mota et al. 1996; Castro et al. 2011).

Nevertheless, semi-arid habitats are home to 42 Centers of Plant Diversity (CPDs) identified by the IUCN, and 40% of Endemic Bird Areas (EBAs) recognized by Birdlife International (White and Nackoney 2003), which is of utmost importance if we consider that the biodiversity crisis is probably the main threat to the future of humanity (Folke et al. 2021). Moreover, these regions also provide a number of essential ecosystem services (e.g. Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2016; Garland et al. 2020). All of this, added to their fragility in the face of natural or anthropogenic events, makes the setting in motion of protective measures for these habitats, along with the conservation of their biodiversity, a priority (Maestre et al. 2012), which is not exempt from social conflicts (Mota et al. 1996; McNeely 2003; Cortes-Vazquez 2014).

In order to favor this protection, it is essential that strategies be designed that improve public knowledge, perception and evaluation as regards these habitats (McNeely 2003), and education may be one such example (López-de-Haro and Segura 2013; Gil de Araujo 2019). The authors of this work thus coordinated a group of educators and researchers from schools located in southeastern Spain, one of the most arid zones in Europe, in an educational research project (López-de-Haro et al. 2011) funded by the autonomous government of Andalusia (Spain). The work revealed the need for a reliable and operative instrument to measure the changes that might occur in the predisposition of students towards the conservation of these places based on a series of instructional sequences. The construct that comes closest to the desired element to be measured is

attitude, a complex concept from which Allport (1935) compiled very diverse interpretations and definitions, many alluding to a favorable or unfavorable predisposition towards the attitude object (Fishbein and Ajzen 1975; Insko and Schopler 1980; Quiles et al. 1998), which in the case we are concerned with are Semi-arid Habitats (SH).

Attitudes and pro-environmental behavior

Pro-environmental behavior can be predicted from factors such as knowledge of the problem and of action strategies, locus of control, attitudes, verbal commitment and sense of individual responsibility (Hines et al. 1987). Twenty years after this proposal, factors that influence pro-environmental behavior have come to be considered as a mixture of social and personal factors, including sense of guilt, social norm, moral guidelines and perceived behavioral control (Bamberg and Möser 2007). More recently, Gifford and Nilsson (2014) have grouped influences on pro-environmental behavior and awareness into 18 factors: childhood experience, knowledge and education, personality and self-construal, sense of control, values, political and world views, goals, felt responsibility, cognitive biases, place attachment, age, gender, chosen activities, religion, urban–rural differences, norms, social class, proximity to problematic environmental sites and cultural and ethnic variations.

Focusing on attitudes, in accordance with the principle of compatibility, the correlation between these and behaviors is much greater when the measured attitude and behavior imply the same action, goal, context and time (Ajzen and Fishbein 1980; Ajzen and Cote 2008). This fact points to it being convenient for the measurement of environmental attitudes to be carried out in relation to specific topics (Moreno et al. 2005). The scale proposed here fulfills this specific requisite as it refers to a very specific attitude object.

People's attitudes toward certain habitats, such as semi-arid ones, can be understood in terms of their perceptions of the positive and negative attributes thereof, in line with the approaches of Allendorf (2007, 2022). For their part, Ntuli et al. (2019) state that "perceptions shape people's attitudes in the very short-run and behaviour in the longer-run", perceptions being what the person knows or understood. It is common in environmental psychology in relation to landscapes for these factors to be considered for both underlying values (priorities or general principles) and those that are assigned (referring to the valued object) (Ives and Kendal 2013; Kiley et al. 2017).

Purposes of the study

The starting premise was that pro-environmental attitudes towards ecosystems (habitats) of arid zones can change following activities designed for such a purpose, but to know if we are really achieving the encouragement of pro-environmental attitudes through educational interventions, it is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of such interventions (Steg and Vlek 2009). In accordance with this idea, the overall aim of this study was to design and test an effective, easy to use tool that we have called PHOto-BASe Attitude Scale towards the COnservation of Semi-Arid Habitats (PHOBASCOSAH). The intention was, furthermore, to increase its applicability to any investigation or activity that requires knowledge of changes in attitudes of participants, whether in formal, non-formal or informal education.

The aforementioned general objective is specified in the following specific objectives:

- a) Select a series of photographs of environmental units representative of semi-arid habitats from the context where the investigation is carried out, in accordance with a number of predefined criteria, which permit the standardization thereof and may be employed in similar investigations.
- b) Identify the most valued attributes of the natural spaces through the relevant literature and own contextualized study.
- c) Determine items to include in the scale from these attributes, the evaluation and contributions from judges-experts and analysis of items.
- d) Test the validity and reliability of the scale through the statistical analysis of its psychometric properties.
- e) Carry out a preliminary analysis of the data obtained in the application of the scale during the construction process thereof, in order to detect possible differences between groups, considering their demographic data, and explore indications of its applicability in other contexts and populations.

METHODS

Context

Semi-arid and arid habitats are distributed over the earth, and occupy 41% of its land surface area ([see map](#)); they are the zones most vulnerable to climate change (Esteve-Selma et al. 2010, 2012) and are home to over a third of the global population (Kimura and Moriyama 2019). The context in which this study has been developed is situated precisely in the most arid zone in Europe, south eastern Spain (Gil Olcina 2009), where the participants in the process reside.

The attitudes scale was constructed and implemented within the framework of the educational research project “Influence of different teaching strategies and methodologies for study of the environment in attitudes towards the conservation of semi-arid habitats”, supported by the Department of Education of the Autonomous Government of Andalusia (File PIV-034/14).

Research participants and sample size

The construction of the scale consisted of various phases during which a total of 490 participants were involved. For each phase different groups were worked with, whose characteristics are summarized in Table 1, associating the phase and purpose of their participation. Participants were selected by convenience sampling, given that it involved complete class-groups of students from the schools that directly participated in the investigation, or collaborating schools. Nevertheless, in the case of the divergent validity test, participants were selected by judgment sampling, involving adults (non-students), of which access was gained to: a group of experts in research or dissemination of semi-arid habitats (n=32) and another without any connection to them (n=43).

Table 1. Participants in each phase of the study

Sampling	n	Age range	Student groups	Phase of the study (and purpose)
1	47	12-15	Secondary students from schools in south eastern Spain	"Reasons for Conservation" Form (<i>Identify features to measure</i>)
2	86	12-15	Secondary students from 6 class-groups from 4 schools in SE Spain.	Pilot study (<i>Item analysis</i>)
3.1	282	13-16 (80 % of 13 and 14-year-olds)	Secondary students from 13 groups from 6 schools in SE Spain	Descriptive statistics, Factorial and reliability analysis
3.2	261	13-16 (80 % of 13 and 14-year-olds)	The same student groups (some did not participate) from above with a 3 months gap.	Complementary analysis (<i>Confirmation of factorial model</i>)
4	32	33-63	Academics, researchers and graduates particularly connected to SH	Complementary analysis (<i>Divergent validity</i>)
5	43	25-65	Graduates and senior technical staff without special connection to SH	

The validation process and the greater part of the statistical analyses were carried out on secondary students from state schools that participated in the aforementioned educational research project (sample 3.1), of which 135 were girls (47.87%), and 147 boys (52.13%).

Instrument for Evaluating Students' attitudes towards the conservation of Semi-Arid Habitats

There is extensive scientific literature on the use of images for assessing landscape preferences (e.g., Arriaza et al. 2004; Kalivoda et al. 2014; Sahraoui et al. 2016; Tieskens et al. 2018). In fact, it has been proven that judgements on photographic scenes have a high correlation with those made by respondents in situ (Shuttleworth 1980; Stewart et al. 1984; Scott and Canter 1997; Daniel and Meitner 2001; Palmer and Hoffman 2001), to which it was considered that their use in this investigation was appropriate.

The methodologies used in studies on landscape preferences are extremely varied: comparison of pairs of photos (Benayas 1991; DeLucio and Múgica 1994); choice of photos from a panel (Arriaza et al. 2004; Barroso et al. 2012; Kalivoda et al. 2014); classification of a group of photographs into different levels of preferences (García-Llorente et al. 2012); score assignment (Tveit 2009); questions or questionnaires on photos (Balling and Falk 1982; Falk and Balling 2010; Hagerhall 2001), and so on. All of them involve establishing preferences and, in some cases, carrying out a qualitative analysis thereof. This was not the objective of PHOBASCOSAH; rather, it was to assess the changes that occur in the perception of a specific habitat, without comparing it to others. Thus, we have opted for a novel alternative, as far as we know, that combines an attitude scale with photos of the habitats in question. Its design required the

implementation of two different processes: the determination of the attitude object via the selection of the habitats to be studied and the selection of the photographs that represent them, and the wording and selection of the items with which these attitudes would be assessed.

Determination of the attitude object

Selection of environmental units (habitats)

To construct the scale, it was necessary to determine a series of environmental units representative of the semi-arid zones in the south east of the Iberian Peninsula. The term “habitat” was chosen due to the fact it is that which is used in Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora, which forms part of Europe's nature conservation policy. It defines *natural habitats* as “terrestrial or aquatic areas distinguished by geographic, abiotic and biotic features, whether entirely natural or semi-natural”. Although this denomination “normally refers to the conditions of the environment, it is used here in the sense that the vegetable community is a good bioindicator of the ecological conditions of the environment” (Alcaraz Ariza et al. 2008). This directive, with the participation of numerous scientists from across Europe supported by their respective governments, included the inventory of over 200 types of habitats of community interest whose conservation is essential. Those selected for this scale were recognizable and linked to the semi-arid south east of Spain, permitting educational activities to be carried out with local students (Table 2). In the case of the habitat 5330 (Thermo-Mediterranean pre-steppe scrub), which occupy by far the greatest part of the surface of the area considered (Valle Tendero et al. 2004), the authors decided to divide them into four units according to type of substratum, given that this has a considerable influence on the characteristics of the setting, with the final selection comprising 11 habitats.

Table 2. Selection of habitats for the creation of the scale. The habitats extracted directly from Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 have been presented alongside the numbering assigned therein. Those lacking numbers are sub-habitats proposed by the authors due to their appropriateness for the study.

No.	Type of habitat	Name in this article	Code assigned
1	COSTAL AND HALOPHYTIC HABITATS		
12	Sea cliffs and shingle or stony beaches	Sea cliffs	Cli
14	Mediterranean and thermo-Atlantic salt marshes and salt meadows	Salt marshes	Sal
15	Salt and gypsum continental steppes		
	Iberian gypsicolous vegetation (<i>Gypsophiletalia</i>)	Gypsum outcrops	Gyp
2	COASTAL SAND DUNES AND CONTINENTAL DUNES		
22	Sea dunes of the Mediterranean coast	Coastal sandbanks	Dun
3	FRESHWATER HABITATS		
32	Running water		
3290	Intermittently flowing Mediterranean rivers of the Paspalo-Agrostidion	Intermittently flowing	Int
5	SCLEROPHYLLOUS SCRUB		
52	Mediterranean arborescent scrub	Arborescent scrub	Arb

53	Thermo-Mediterranean and pre-steppe scrub		
5330	Thermo-Mediterranean and pre-steppe scrub		
	Thermo-Mediterranean and pre-steppe scrub on badlands	Badlands	Bad
	Thermo-Mediterranean and pre-steppe scrub on calcareous substrates	Calcareous scrubs	Cal
	Thermo-Mediterranean and pre-steppe scrub on siliceous substrates	Siliceous scrubs	Sil
	Thermo-Mediterranean and pre-steppe scrub on volcanic substrates	Volcanic scrubs	Vol
8	ROCKY HABITATS AND CAVES		
82	Rocky slopes with chasmophytic vegetation	Rocky slopes	Roc

Selection of images (photos)

It was necessary to standardize the photographs to minimize any difference between them that might have had an influence on the evaluation of the participants, and that bore no relationship to the defining characteristics of the habitat in question (vegetation and soils, predominantly). Taking into account the proposals of different authors (Balling and Falk 1982; Hagerhall 2000; Kiley et al. 2017), the recommendations of two experienced nature photographers and the research objectives, the following photo selection criteria were set:

- Minimal technical correction (exposure, focus, framing, sharpness...).
- Similar lighting conditions: frontlight (sun behind the photographer, without backlight or shadow zones), sunny days, avoiding dawn, midday and dusk.
- Similar scale, with predominance of mid-range shots in which vegetation is distinguished, but without close range shots, and placement of observer (photographer) slightly elevated but without wide panoramic shots.
- Horizontal 4:3 format.
- Similar environmental conditions that show the “standard” features of the habitat, with well-developed vegetation, avoiding very dry, wet or flowering periods.
- Without presence of animals.
- Without presence of humans or constructions.

An initial selection resulted in the compilation of 40 photographs, provided or taken ex profeso by various photographers. As well as the aforementioned criteria, it was also taken into account that the photos be truly representative of the habitats (Kiley et al. 2017). Thus, the final selection of the 11 photographs, one from each of the selected habitats, involved the participation of a botanist expert in SH and a teacher, the co-authors of this article, together with a collaborating nature photographer.

Item redaction process

As already indicated, attitudes can derive from the positive or negative perception of the attributes of each habitat, to which the redaction of the items requires the identification of said attributes. To this end, a prior study was undertaken that included

a survey on a group of participants corresponding to sample 1 via a Google form entitled “Reasons for conserving”. This survey included a photo of a landscape from the Aigües tortes i Estany de Sant Maurici National Park (Spain) and the following text: “Briefly explain the reasons you think a residential complex should not be built in the place shown in the photo”. The results can be seen in Table 3, along with those obtained by Allendorf (2022) in a review of attitudes towards protected areas throughout the world, and those from the classic study by Margules and Usher (1981) on criteria for prioritizing natural reserves. It is also important to draw attention to the fact that scenic attractiveness has been identified as one of the factors that bears the most influence on the perceived conservation value of a landscape (Kiley et al. 2017).

Table 3. Valued attributes in protected areas in various studies, in order of the frequency with which they were used.

Own study	Allendorf (2022)	Margules and Usher (1981)
Conservation of Biodiversity (100%)	Conservation of biodiversity and regulating services (89%)	Diversity (including species richness and habitat diversity) (89%)
Conservation of natural environment and landscape (49%)	Limitations on extraction and use (80%)	Rarity (78%)
Pollution (38%)	Wildlife conflicts (77%)	Naturalness (78%)
Aesthetic reasons (32%)	Protected areas management, projects, and private enterprise (73%)	Area (67%)
Ecosystem services (21%)	Assistance from protected areas management and community development Programs (57%)	Threat of human interference (67%)
Economic and viability reasons (21%)	Employment and income benefits (57%)	Typicalness or representativeness (44%)
Other unrepeated individual reasons.	Resource extraction (49%)	Educational value (33%)
	Land loss and no agricultural expansion (33%)	Amenity value (33%)
	Recreation and aesthetic benefits (23%)	Recorded history (33%)
	Cultural benefits (3%)	Other less representative criteria.

The project coordinator prepared a first initial proposal of 18 items taking into consideration these features, the characteristics of the SH selected and the age of the participants in the study. Following an adaptation of the Delphi method, this proposal, together with the purpose of the scale and the requirements that the items had to fulfill, was presented in a meeting to a group of 11 experts, secondary education teachers in different disciplines of the natural sciences, along with a psychologist-adviser, who worked in schools in the study zone and participated in the investigation. They were asked to add other items they considered to be of interest and reject those that, in their opinion, were not appropriate. As a result of this initial phase a proposal of 37 items was obtained, which was shared with everyone online in order for them to select those they

thought should remain included in the final version of the scale. In view of the results of this phase, first, the items chosen by at least 9 experts were selected. Then, those they considered redundant were eliminated and those with the greatest consensus regarding lesser represented components or features were retrieved in order to achieve a balanced proposal. The redaction was revised according to the suggestions on language, syntax and content proposed by Corbetta (2013). Likewise, the orientation of some items was changed to obtain a balance between those that were favorable and unfavorable towards the attitude object in order to avoid acquiescence bias (Ferrando et al. 2011; Louzán Mariño 2020). The proposal finally stood at 16 items, which were again presented to the experts and obtained their consensus.

To respond to each of these 16 items a Likert scale of 5 options was used (from strongly disagree to strongly agree) for each of the 11 selected habitats. Using Google Forms, each page included a photo of a habitat and the 16 items in a grid with the five options on level of agreement (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Section of an area of the PHOBASCOSAH.

2

	Muy en desacuerdo	En desacuerdo	Indiferente	De acuerdo	Muy de acuerdo
Aquí viven gran cantidad de especies.	<input type="radio"/>				
Esta zona es improductiva y es necesario transformarla en cultivos.	<input type="radio"/>				
Esta zona no tiene ningún interés paisajístico.	<input type="radio"/>				

Pilot test and item analysis

Once this first version of the questionnaire was created, a pilot test was carried out on 86 participants (sample 2, Table 1). The questionnaire was completed individually online but in the classroom under the supervision of the corresponding teacher, who communicated a reference number to each participant to guarantee anonymity but allow the responses to be compared to the other questionnaires. The instructions necessary for completion were offered in writing in the questionnaire itself and all responses were marked as obligatory, in such a way that it was not possible to access the following page (next habitat) without having answered all of those on the previous page.

Due to a recording error there was a partial loss of data and it was decided to eliminate three habitats from the analysis: *Sal, Arb and Roc*. An analysis of items was carried out with the rest of the data via an item-total correlation and obtaining of reliability via Cronbach's alpha coefficient and McDonald's omega (recommended for ordinal scales) using the program IBM SPSS Statistics 28.0.1.0. Given that the objective was to obtain a group of items applicable to all habitats, in order to select them, the following quantitative and qualitative criteria were taken into account for all of the habitats at the same time:

- The corrected correlation of the sum of the total items (item-total correlation minus item in question)
- The variation of Cronbach's alpha coefficient with the elimination of the item
- If confusing or redundant.
- The balance between the aspects to be measured, along with items favorable and unfavorable towards the attitude object.

6 items were eliminated in accordance with these criteria, with the final scale comprising 10 (see Table 4).

Table 4: Final questionnaire items with the corresponding code and whether it involves a favorable (+) or unfavorable (-) statement towards the attitude object.

Item	Code	Favorable / Unfavorable sense
1. A large quantity of different plant and animal species live here.	<i>Spec</i>	+
2. This zone is unproductive and it is necessary to transform it into crops.	<i>Tran</i>	-
3. This zone is of no scenic interest.	<i>Nsce</i>	-
4. The destruction or alteration of this landscape should be sanctioned.	<i>Sanc</i>	+
5. There is scarcely any life in these landscapes	<i>Nlif</i>	-
6. Not much would be lost if species disappeared from this zone.	<i>Exti</i>	-
7. It would be worth investing in the conservation of this zone.	<i>Inve</i>	+
8. I like this landscape.	<i>Like</i>	+
9. There are only insignificant bushes here.	<i>Bush</i>	-
10. This place is inhabited by rare, scarce or threatened species.	<i>Rare</i>	+

Data analysis

This final scale of 10 items was given to sample 3.1 ($n=282$; Table 1), but this time only for the habitats *Bad*, *Int* and *Cal* (see Fig. 2) which were going to be worked within the study, in a way that the data obtained served as a pretest thereof. The procedure used was the same as for the pilot test. The data obtained in this phases were employed in all of the analyses outlined below.

Fig. 2 Photos of the three habitats worked within the study (*Bad*, *Cal* and *Int*, from left to right).

Once again IBM SPSS Statistics was used for the descriptive statistics and to confirm any differences between groups, to which the Mann-Whitney U test was used, applied to the responses from both sexes and, as there were individuals who originated from different countries and cultures amongst the students, it was thought interesting to verify whether this aspect had an influence on the answers to the different items, to which this technique was also used for the two unrelated groups.

Following the recommendations of Pérez and Medrano (2010), a preliminary analysis of the data was carried out to confirm the fulfillment of the statistical hypotheses required in order to subject them to the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). Firstly, data was explored to detect univariate outliers, to which the Z-score for each item were calculated, and for multivariate cases, for which the Mahalanobis distance (D^2) was used. Those Z-scores outside the ± 3 range were considered as univariate outlier and those with a significance value of $p < 0.001$ (Hair et al. 2014) were considered to be multivariate. The normality study was implemented by calculating the skewness and kurtosis indices, with values within the ± 1 range considered to be adequate (Ferrando and Anguiano-Carrasco 2010). The Mardia coefficient and its significance value were obtained for multivariate normality. The linearity and multicollinearity diagnosis was tested via the curve estimation, analyzing the bivariate correlations of all of the variables from Spearman's rho and via the variance inflation factor (VIF) and tolerance (Pérez and Medrano 2010).

For the factor analysis, following the recommendations of Brown (2006), sample 3.1 ($n=282$; Table 1) was randomly divided into two sub-samples (both $n=141$). One was subjected to the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and the other to the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), to test the cross-validity or independence of the samples used

(Aitkin 1968; Anastasi and Urbina 1998). The program FACTOR v10.10.03 (Ferrando and Lorenzo-Seva 2017) was used for the EFA, or Unrestricted Factor Analysis, as these authors prefer to call it. Bartlett's test of sphericity value and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) index were calculated to confirm the appropriateness of the data for carrying out the factor analysis. As the hypotheses for accrediting the multivariate normality were not fulfilled, a polychoric matrix was used (Dominguez Lara 2014) along with the Unweighted Least-Squares method (ULS), recommended for ordinal data with distributions that fail to comply with normality criteria (Forero et al. 2009), with the employment of polychoric correlations (Freiberg Hoffmann et al. 2013) or small sample sizes (Jung 2013). The EFA was calculated for one, two, three and four factors. The decision on the factor model that would be tested in the CFA was taken based on the results of these analyses, their interpretation, that proposed by the Parallel Analysis procedure (Optimal implementation of Parallel Analysis) (Timmerman and Lorenzo-Seva 2011) and the indices that assess residual correlations, Gamma Index (GFI) and Root Mean Squared Residual (RMSR), the Lavaan 0.6-7 R package was used for the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), again employing the ULS method and the polychoric correlations matrix. To determine the goodness of fit of the proposed model the following indices were calculated: Chi squared between degrees of freedom (χ^2/df), the Bentler-Bonett Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), the normalized Root Mean Square Error of Approximation index (RMSEA) and the Gamma Index (GFI).

To estimate the reliability of the scale, the degree of internal consistency was calculated through Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's Omega, recommended for ordinal data that do not fulfill the tau-equivalent (Ventura-León and Caycho-Rodríguez 2017), for each of the three habitats selected (*Bad*, *Cal* and *Int*), using the answers to the scale from the entire sample 3.1 ($n= 282$).

Complementary analyses

The current interpretation of the validity of a test refers to the degree in which its scores are reinforced by empirical theory and evidence (AERA, APA and NCME 1999). It is considered a dynamic and open process that affords credibility to a scale and its usefulness (Vallejo et al. 2003; Prieto and Delgado 2010). In this regard, as this scale was also used in the posttest of the aforementioned investigation, it was decided to subject the data obtained in this one to a CFA, this time on sample 3.2 ($n=261$; Table 1), to check whether the proposed unifactorial model was again confirmed. With a segmentation of these data, those corresponding to the students who had participated in a teaching intervention that included a field trip ($n=79$), a differentiated CFA was carried out to confirm the reasons for the relatively low factorial weight of the *Rare* item.

To gather more evidence on its validity, the scale was used with two groups (samples 4 and 5; Table 1) for which, due to their relationship with the attitude object, different scores were expected: one group with a professional connection to SH and committed to their conservation ($n=32$), and another without this connection ($n=43$). A contrast of hypotheses was made with the Mann-Whitney U and Wilcoxon W test for two

independent samples. This test was made for each of the 11 initial habitats to see whether the scale differentiated these groups, and therefore be useful, in regard to all of them.

Ethical approval declarations

All of the protocols and procedures developed were included in the project approved by the already cited Department of Education of the Autonomous Government of Andalusia. The participating schools were included in this project and reflected the fact in their planning documentation. The participants were informed from the beginning, showing their acceptance at participating on a voluntary basis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The process described in Methods for the selection of the items, in which 11 teachers and researchers (judges/experts) participated, supports the content validation of the scale, which in educational spheres is normally carried out through the consultation of experts (Prieto and Delgado 2010). These authors, however, also indicate that using terms such as content validity, predictive, factorial..., is not completely rigorous; rather, it involves different facets of a single integrating concept. The following sections should be interpreted in this sense.

Pilot study

In this pilot study, the 16 items selected by the judges and subject to testing presented a homogeneity index (corrected item-total correlation) above the recommended value of 0.3 (Frias-Navarro 2021) for all of the habitats, with almost all of them showing a correlation above 0.45. The only item under these values was *Rare*, which for the *Cli* habitat had an index of 0.223. This value was situated above the limit recommended by Frías-Navarro (2021) for eliminating items and, additionally, its elimination did not substantially raise the value of the reliability index. After the analysis of the items, 10 of them were selected following the criteria indicated in the methods section. The Cronbach's Alpha and McDonald's Omega coefficient of the resulting scales showed, in all of the habitats, values clearly above 0.70 (Table 5), considered sufficient for an adequate reliability based on internal consistency (Kaplan and Saccuzzo 2018; Prieto and Delgado 2010).

Table 5. Consistency analysis values via Cronbach's Alpha in the pilot test

	Int	Bad	Dun	Cal	Cli	Vol	Gyp	Sil
CRONBACH'S ALPHA	0.775	0.839	0.819	0.810	0.832	0.815	0.851	0.850
MCDONALD'S OMEGA	0.771	0.839	0.814	0.802	0.828	0.809	0.848	0.850

Preliminary data analysis

The following analyses were made with the scale of 10 items and the three habitats selected for the subsequent educational investigation (*Bad*, *Cal* and *Int*), applied to

sample 3.1 ($n = 282$, Table 1). The descriptive statistics (Table 6) revealed a fairly homogenous attitude towards conservation of all SH and the different items, with mean values ranging in almost all cases between 3 and 4 (indifferent/agree). The exception is the *Rare* item, with a score slightly below 3 for the three habitats.

Table 6. Mean (M) and Standard Deviation (SD) of the items for the three habitats analyzed.

Item	Badlands (<i>Bad</i>)		Calcareous scrubs (<i>Cal</i>)		Intermittently flowing (<i>Int</i>)	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
A large quantity of different plant and animal species live here (<i>Spec</i>)	3.12	1.050	3.54	1.103	3.36	1.069
This zone is unproductive and it is necessary to transform it into crops (<i>Tran</i>)	3.38	1.167	3.66	1.099	3.27	1.233
This zone is of no scenic interest (<i>Nsce</i>)	3.52	1.126	3.88	1.050	3.43	1.247
The destruction or alteration of this landscape should be sanctioned (<i>Sanc</i>)	3.51	1.261	3.56	1.352	3.55	1.391
There is scarcely any life in these landscapes (<i>Nlif</i>)	3.40	1.172	3.84	1.089	3.51	1.117
Not much would be lost if species disappeared from this zone (<i>Exti</i>)	3.94	1.016	4.09	0.973	4.16	1.017
It would be worth investing in the conservation of this zone (<i>Inve</i>)	3.71	1.034	3.74	1.036	3.71	1.061
I like this landscape (<i>Like</i>)	3.61	1.101	3.91	1.087	3.46	1.184
There are only insignificant bushes here (<i>Bush</i>)	3.78	1.074	4.01	0.989	3.86	1.142
This place is inhabited by rare, scarce or threatened species (<i>Rare</i>)	2.84	1.103	2.93	1.144	2.82	1.211
Mean of all habitat items	3.48		3.72		3.51	

The hypothesis contrast via the Mann-Whitney U test, carried out to compare the differences between sexes, only revealed significant differences for the *Nlif* item from a single habitat, *Int* ($p=0.002$), with a higher score in the case of the women (average range 155.64 compared to 126.10), and for *Nsce* from *Cal* (151.02-131.13; $p=0.031$). It is a case of differences in two variables of the 30 analysed (three habitats with 10 items each); moreover, no item shows differences in all habitats, nor does any habitat in all or the majority of the items, to which these small variations do not seem to follow any pattern or bias.

Applying the same test to the students according to their origin, it is observed that Spanish students obtained a significantly higher score than those originating from other countries in the item "The destruction or alteration of this landscape should be sanctioned" (*Sanc*), which also occurs in the case of the three habitats *Int* ($p= 0.000$; 150.43-106.25), *Bad* ($p=0.02$; 148.73-112.96) and *Cal* ($p=0.04$; 148,40-114,28), as well as the item *Inve* for the habitat *Cal* ($p=0.018$; 147.02-119.71). With these data we cannot be certain whether these differences are due to the bias of the item or to a real difference in the groups analysed in regards to the feature measured thereby (Gómez-Benito and Hidalgo 2010). If the difference is real the term impact is used (Ackerman 1992); in contrast, if the causes are unknown, it is common to speak of Differential Item

Functioning (DIF), a term coined by Holland and Thayer (1986). In view of the lack of a complementary study in this regard, and considering that students of other nationalities comprise 20% of the sample, it was decided to eliminate the item *Sanc* from the scale. In any event, this finding is in harmony with the work of García-Llorente et al. (2012) in a geographical context similar to that used in this study, which found that people with no connection to a territory were less disposed towards collaborating economically in its conservation, which may be relevant for landscape preference studies that frequently employ so-called monetary techniques.

Once the data for the *Sanc* item were removed, the data for the other 9 items were subject to an analysis prior to the undertaking of the EFA. There were no missing data. Regarding the univariate outliers, 9 were found for the *Cal* habitat corresponding to 2 items, 4 for *Int*, corresponding to a single item, and none were found for *Bad*. As regards outliers multivariate, 3 were identified in the *Cal* habitat and one in each of the other two. The univariate outliers present scores very close to the $Z \pm 3$ value taken as a reference, which in samples $n > 80$ can rise to $Z \pm 4$ (Hair et al. 2014), to which it was decided to maintain these data.

In terms of skewness statistics, the items *Nvid* and *Like* in the *Cal* habitat and *Exti* in *Wat* slightly exceeded the $-1/+1$ threshold. Regarding kurtosis, *Trans* in *Wat* and *Nvid* in *Cal* exceeded this range. Nevertheless, they were all found within the $-1.5/+1.5$ range, which can be considered a slight variation from normality and, therefore, appropriate for submitting to an EFA (George and Mallery 2003). The same does not occur with multivariate normality. In all cases, Mardia test values above the significance value ($p < 0.05$) were obtained for asymmetry ($p=1$), but not for kurtosis ($p=0.000$), indicating that the multivariate normality hypothesis is not fulfilled for the latter. The curve estimation and magnitude of the Spearman Rho in the bivariate correlation matrix, which obtains significant values in 88% of cases, suggest linearity. The absence of multicollinearity is indicated by the fact that none of the correlation coefficients are higher than 0.90. This is further confirmed by the tolerance indices being greater than 0.10 and the VIF indices being greater than 10 in all cases (Pérez and Medrano 2010).

Exploratory factor analysis

The EFA was carried out using the scores from half of the M3.1 sample ($n=141$), with the values from Bartlett's test of sphericity being optimum and those of the KMO sufficient, and somewhat low for the *Cal* habitat (see all results in Table 7). Various factorial solutions were tested, but those of more than one factor were difficult to interpret and did not show sufficient variables with substantial weighting in each factor. The unifactorial model presented RMSR values somewhat higher than the Kelly criterion, but the GFI was optimum in two habitats and acceptable in another, and the Parallel Analysis would suggest the solution of a single factor in all cases. Furthermore, the factor loadings were situated above the recommended 0.30 (Bandalos and Finney 2019) in all cases, save for the variable *Rare* in the *Int* habitat (0.276), an aspect that shall be discussed further on. This led to the adoption of the unifactorial model, which was, in addition, the most parsimonious.

Table 7. Results of the EFA and values considered optimum and acceptable for facilitating its interpretation.

	Bartlett's test spher.	KMO	GFI	RMSR	Variance explained by single factor
Optimum adjustment	$p < 0.05$	> 0.79	> 0.95	Harman's criterion ≤ 0.05	
Acceptable adjustment		Between 0.70 and 0.79	Between 0.90 and 0.95	Kelly criterion $< 1/\sqrt{N} = 0.0845$	
<i>Bad</i>	0.00001	0.758	0.963	0.0988	42.77 %
<i>Cal</i>	0.00001	0.681	0.934	0.1255	38.78 %
<i>Int</i>	0.00001	0.788	0.969	0.0867	40.46 %

Confirmatory factor analysis

With the data from the other half of sample 3.1 ($n = 141$) the proposed unifactorial model was put to the test via CFA. As can be seen in Table 8, the results indicated an adjustment between acceptable and optimum for all of the habitats in the CFI, TLI, χ^2/gl and GFI indices. The values for the RMSEA are close the limit considered as acceptable for the *Bad* habitat, but markedly above this for the other habitats.

Table 8. Results of the CFA and values considered optimum and acceptable for facilitating its interpretation.

	CFI	TLI	χ^2/gl	RMSEA	GFI
Optimum adjustment	> 0.95	> 0.95	≤ 2	< 0.05	> 0.95
Acceptable adjustment	> 0.90	> 0.90	≤ 3	< 0.08	> 0.90
<i>Bad</i>	0.944	0.926	1.912	0.081	0.992
<i>Cal</i>	0.972	0.962	1.570	0.056	0.994
<i>Int</i>	0.973	0.963	1.455	0.057	0.993

Moreover, as shown in Fig. 3, the factor loadings were all above the recommended 0.3 (Bandalos and Finney 2019), except for the *Tran* item in the *Bad* habitat and, above all, the *Rare* item in all of the habitats.

Fig. 3. Factor loadings and calculated error (e_1, e_2, \dots) of the different items of the PHOBASCOSAH for each of the habitats in the single factor *Attitude towards CONservation of Semi-Arid Habitats* (ACOSAH).

The low value of the factor loading for the *Rare* item seems to be related to the low score for this item compared to the rest, which we observe in the descriptive statistics. It appears that it is not conceivable for such apparently “poor” landscapes to be able to host species of special interest. If this were the case, the item could be very sensitive (and very useful as a result) to teaching interventions implemented in the investigation cited in the introduction, and this could balance their factorial weighting in the scale. To test this hypothesis, a CFA was carried out on the posttest data of this study, but segmenting those of the individuals of the experimental group that had participated in the teaching intervention that included a field trip (n=79), in which it had been proven that significant changes were produced. As Fig. 4 shows, the factorial weighting of this item rises in all cases clearly above the recommended 0.3, which appears to confirm this idea.

Fig. 4. Factor loadings of the different items resulting from the CFA on the data from the posttest of the participants in the teaching intervention with field trip.

Internal consistency

In regards to the estimation of the reliability of these scales via their degree of internal consistency, the values obtained for the Chronbach’s Alpha and McDonald’s Omega (see

Table 9), calculated with the whole of sample 3.1 ($n=282$), are higher than the recommended 0.70. It was also calculated for all of the habitats at the same time (27 items), with the thinking that they could be simultaneously applied in some studies, in this case obtaining a higher value.

Table 9. Consistency analysis values via Cronbach's Alpha.

	TOTAL (sum)	Int	Bad	Cal
CRONBACH'S ALPHA	0.871	0.756	0.756	0.743
MCDONALD'S OMEGA	0.862	0.754	0.755	0.733

Complementary analyses

In the CFA carried out on the data obtained in the posttest of the aforementioned investigation ($n=261$, Table 1) a number of indices of optimum adjustment are obtained (Table 9), which confirms that the unifactorial model of the scale is adequate. In Fig. 5 the factor loadings obtained can be seen, in which the *Rare* item only has a factor loading under 0.3 in the *Cal* habitat.

Table 10. Results of the CFA and values considered optimum and acceptable for facilitating its interpretation.

	CFI	TLI	χ^2/df	RMSEA	GFI
Optimum adjustment	>0.95	>0.95	≤ 2	<0.05	>0.95
Acceptable adjustment	>0.90	>0.90	≤ 3	<0.08	>0.90
Bad	0.922	0.989	1.474	0.043	0.997
Cal	0.996	0.994	1.245	0.031	0.998
Int	0.995	0.994	1.219	0.029	0.997

Fig. 5. Factor loadings of the different items resulting from the CFA on the data from the posttest of all participants in the cited investigation.

To further support the utility and validity of the scale, the Mann-Whitney U and Wilcoxon W tests were carried out. Applying the scales to sample 4 (individuals with a connection to and special commitment towards SH, n=32) and 5 (people with no special connection to SH, n=43), it was shown that the average ranges of people linked to these habitats were higher in all of them. These differences were significant in all cases except for the *Sal* habitat (see Table 11), the least valued by sample 4 and the most by sample 5. This may be due to being a habitat that, in the photo that appeared in the scale, shows vegetation cover of almost 100%, which has been valued by sample 5 (phytophilia) but is perhaps the least biodiverse habitat. This appears to indicate that the scale loses effectiveness for those habitats that are not arid, semi-arid or degraded with modest coverage, the ones that lack social consensus on the need for their protection. However, the scale perfectly distinguished the two groups in the rest of the habitats, which can be considered as further proof of its validity. Taking into account the socio-demographic characteristics of these groups, the results indicate that the scale could be used in others different to those for which they were designed (students aged from 12 to 16).

Table 11. Results of the hypothesis contrast on the responses of the group of individuals with a connection to SH (sample 4) and the group with no connection to these habitats (sample 5).

Habitat	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymptotic significance (bilateral)
Wat	449	1395	-2.569	0.010
Bad	291.5	1237.5	-4.278	0.000
Dun	458.5	1404.5	-2.472	0.013
Arb	394	1340	-3.18	0.001
Sal	660.5	1606.5	-0.296	0.767
Roc	412.5	1358.5	-2.969	0.003
Cal	477.5	1423.5	-2.265	0.024
Cli	461	1407	-2.477	0.013
Vol	367.5	1313.5	-3.476	0.001
Gyp	346.5	1292.5	-3.705	0.000
Sil	448.5	1394.5	-2.585	0.010
Total	401.5	1347.5	-3.07	0.002

Study limitations

The participants were selected by a non-probability sampling method but, as they originated from complete classroom-groups from different towns (Table 1), it could be considered as a relatively representative sample. Moreover, despite all of them residing in eastern Almeria, the diversity of their origins could be considered indicative of the applicability of the scale in other geographical spheres, although this should be done

with caution. Likewise, although it has been demonstrated that the scale effectively differentiates groups according to attitude towards SH in adults, on the whole it has been constructed with students aged 13-14, to which we must be prudent with the age range it is used with.

The *Rare* item presents a low factor loading in the FA, indicating a weak correlation with the single factor. As we have seen, this problem disappears when the participants have received a certain amount of training, being the item most sensitive to the teaching intervention and one of the technical criteria most taken into consideration in the protection of the territory (Margules and Usher 1981; Martínez-Hernández et al. 2009, 2011). For studies with other objectives it will be necessary to value the appropriateness or not of its elimination.

Lastly, it has not been possible to analyse the so-called concurrent validity or comparison with another similar already validated instrument given that no scale has been found that refers to the construct studied here.

CONCLUSIONS

The undervaluation of areas with high environmental value such as semi-arid habitats highlights the need for both educational strategies that promote their appreciation in order to achieve their adequate valuation and conservation, and the design of instruments to evaluate the effectiveness of such strategies. In this study we focus on generating a valid and reliable instrument for measuring the changes that occur in attitudes, one of the main factors strongly related to pro-environmental behaviors.

Since the intention was to verify the changes that occur in the perception of a certain habitat without comparing it with others, the usual techniques of landscape preferences based on comparisons or establishment of a ranking were inadequate. For this reason, an instrument has been developed that integrates a 9-item Likert-type attitude scale of five options with photos of the habitats to be evaluated (PHOBASCOSAH), whose results indicate a unifactorial structure, and its psychometric properties support its validity and reliability to a sufficient degree to be used in educational research with students aged 12 to 14.

The procedure followed for the construction of the items can be considered a methodological contribution in itself. The same occurs with the selection of the habitats, based on the European Union legislative framework for biodiversity conservation and the photographs, selected employing criteria that are standardized and possible to replicate in similar tests for arid zones in any geographical sphere.

The analysis of the responses to the scale reveals two interesting findings. The first is the Differential Item Functioning (DIF) with economic implications ("The destruction or alteration of this landscape should be sanctioned"), as significantly less favorable scores were obtained from students originating from other countries, coinciding with other research in a similar geographical context. This result should encourage future works

that test whether it involves a bias or real difference between groups and be taken into account in investigations on the evaluation of landscapes that use so-called monetary techniques. The second finding of great interest refers to the ignorance of rare or threatened species in semi-arid zones. It involves the most undervalued attribute in all of the habitats, something that has important ramifications in terms of proposing educational interventions to improve attitudes thereto. It has been confirmed that the score for this item improves considerably in students who have participated in the process, which meant that its factor loading increases afterwards. This behavior makes it a prime target and it is, moreover, an attribute inherent to the biota of arid zones, among which endemic and rare species are frequent.

The results of the pilot test show the transferability of the scale, which could be useful for any habitat where there is no social consensus on the need for its conservation, or even for recognising the existence or non-existence of this consensus during the discussion period prior to a declaration as protected zone. This aspect is very important in zones whose conservation frequently creates social and economic conflict. Furthermore, the complementary investigations carried out show that it could be used with ages different from those of the participants in this study. It is, therefore, an instrument that may be useful for the evaluation of any educational activity that has the purpose of producing changes in participant attitudes towards the conservation of these such singular and undervalued habitats, be it in the sphere of formal, non-formal or informal education, and for making comparisons between groups, establishing profiles or detecting sources of conflict.

Acknowledgments

To the Department of Education of the Autonomous Government of Andalusia (Spain), which approved the educational research project (File PIV-034/14) which gave rise to this study. To the teaching staff who participated in it: María Ballester Beltrán, José M. Calahorra García, Esther Gálvez Jiménez, Anabel González Carmona, Vanessa Olivares Gómez, Victoria Pamies Pacheco, Rosario Ruiz Román, María Luisa Sánchez Cano, Víctor Serrano Virgil, Ana J. Sola Gómez, Marcos Diéguez Vidal, Josefa Tomás Ruiz and Alberto Torres Rubio. To Francisca L. Fernández Ortega for his active participation and theoretical contributions on attitudes. To Pedro de la Rosa Flores for his invaluable assistance in the selection of the photographs. To David Aguilera Morales for his constructive criticism and methodological suggestions. To Diego Fernando Rivera Camacho for his clarifications on factor analysis and structural equations. Thanks to CEIP Ntra. Sra. Del Rosario, Ecoescuela de Guazamara, because it is where the project was created. This research has been sponsored by Projects PID2020-116097RB-I00 (Ministry of Science and Innovation of Spain), UAL2020-SEJ-D1784 FEDER (European Regional Development Fund) and P20_00094 (Andalusian Government) and European Union's Horizon 2020 (H2020-MSCA-RISE-777803).

Statements and Declarations

Funding

This work has been partially financed by the projects PGC2018-097988-A-I00, PID2020-116097RB-I00, and UAL2020-SEJ-D1784 funded by FEDER/Ministry of Science and Innovation (MCI) of Spain-State Research Agency (AEI) and P20_00094 funded by Andalusia Government.

Compliance with ethical standards

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

All respondents were made aware of voluntary participation and have approved.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: Francisco López-de-Haro, María Martínez-Chico, Fabián Martínez-Hernández, Juan Francisco Mota Poveda; Data curation: Francisco López-de-Haro; Software: Javier López-Tomás; Formal analysis: Francisco López-de-Haro, Javier López Tomás, Juan Francisco Mota Poveda; Supervision: Francisco López-de-Haro, María Martínez-Chico, Juan Francisco Mota Poveda; Funding acquisition: María Martínez-Chico, Juan Francisco Mota Poveda; Investigation: Francisco López-de-Haro, Fabián Martínez-Hernández, Juan Francisco Mota Poveda; Visualization: Francisco López-de-Haro, Javier López Tomás, María Martínez-Chico, Fabián Martínez-Hernández, Juan Francisco Mota Poveda; Methodology: Francisco López-de-Haro, María Martínez-Chico, Juan Francisco Mota Poveda; Writing-original draft: Francisco López-de-Haro; Project administration: Francisco López-de-Haro, Juan Francisco Mota Poveda; Writing-review and edition: Francisco López-de-Haro, Javier López Tomás, María Martínez-Chico, Fabián Martínez-Hernández, Juan Francisco Mota Poveda. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Data availability

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- Ackerman TA (1992) A didactic explanation of item bias, item impact, and item validity from a multidimensional perspective. *J Educ Meas* 29(1):67–91. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-3984.1992.tb00368.x>
- Aitkin MA (1968) *Test Theory*. D. Magnusson, Reading, Massachusetts: Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, 1966. *J Am Stat Assoc* 63(321):379–380. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1968.11009260>

- Ajzen I, Cote NG (2008) Attitudes and prediction of behavior. In: Crano D, Prislin R (eds) Attitudes and attitude change, Psychology Press, New York-London, pp 289-311
- Ajzen J, Fishbein M (1980) Understanding attitudes and predicting social behavior. Englewood Cliffs, Prentice-Hall, New Jersey
- Alcaraz Ariza F, Barreña Cayuela JA, Clemente Díaz M, González Garnés AJ, López Bernal J, Rivera Núñez D, Ríos Ruiz S (2008) Manual de interpretación de los hábitats naturales y seminaturales de la Región de Murcia. Hábitats y sistemas de hábitats. Dirección General del Medio Natural. Consejería de Desarrollo Sostenible y Ordenación del Territorio, Murcia
- Allendorf TD (2007) Residents' attitudes toward three protected areas in southwestern Nepal. *Biodivers Conserv* 16:2087–2102. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-006-9092-z>
- Allendorf TD (2022) A global summary of local residents' perceptions of benefits and problems of protected areas. *Biodivers Conserv* 31(2):379–396. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-022-02359-z>
- Allport G (1935). Attitudes. In: Murchison C (ed) A Handbook of Social Psychology. New York: Clark University, New York pp 798-844
- American Educational Research Association, American Psychological Association y National Council on Measurement in Education (1999) Standards for educational and psychological testing. American Educational Research Association. Washington, DC
- Anastasi A, Urbina S (1998) Tests psicológicos. Pearson Educación, México
- Andrade R, Larson KL, Hondula DM, Franklin J (2019) Social–Spatial Analyses of Attitudes toward the Desert in a Southwestern U.S. City. *Ann Am Assoc Geogr* 109(6):1845–1864. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2019.1580498>
- Appleton J (1996) *The experience of landscape*. Wiley, University of Michigan
- Arriaza M, Cañas-Ortega JF, Cañas-Madueño JA, Ruiz-Aviles P (2004) Assessing the visual quality of rural landscapes. *Landsc Urban Plan* 69(1):115–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2003.10.029>
- Balling JD, Falk JH (1982) Development of Visual Preference for Natural Environments. *Environ Behav* 14(1):5–28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916582141001>
- Bamberg S, Möser G (2007) Twenty years after Hines, Hungerford, and Tomera: A new meta-analysis of psycho-social determinants of pro-environmental behaviour. *J Environ Psychol* 27(1):14–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2006.12.002>
- Bandalos DL, Finney SJ (2019) Factor Analysis: Exploratory and Confirmatory. In: Hancock GR, Mueller RO (eds) *Reviewer's guide to quantitative methods*. Routledge, New York. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315755649-8>
- Barroso FL, Pinto-Correia T, Ramos IL, Surová D, Menezes H (2012) Dealing with landscape fuzziness in user preference studies: Photo-based questionnaires in the Mediterranean context. *Landsc Urban Plan* 104(3-4):329–342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2011.11.005>

- Benayas J (1991) Paisaje y educación ambiental: evaluación de cambios de actitudes hacia el entorno. Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid
- Bernáldez FG (1981) Ecología y paisaje. H. Blume. Madrid
- Bernáldez FG (1985) Invitación a la ecología humana: La adaptación afectiva al entorno. Tecnos. Spain
- Brown TA (2006) Confirmatory factor analysis for applied research. The Guilford Press, New York
- Castro AJ, Martín-López B, García-Llorente M, Aguilera PA, López E, Cabello J (2011) Social preferences regarding the delivery of ecosystem services in a semiarid Mediterranean region. *J Arid Environ* 75(11):1201–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2011.05.013>
- Corbetta P (2013) Metodología y técnicas de investigación social. McGraw-Hill Interamericana de España, Madrid
- Cortes-Vazquez JA (2014) Protected Areas, Conservation Stakeholders and the ‘Naturalisation’ of Southern Europe. *Forum Dev Stud* 41(2):183–205. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08039410.2014.901238>
- Daniel TC, Meitner MM (2001) Representational validity of landscape visualizations: The effects of graphical realism on perceived scenic beauty of forest vistas. *J Environ Psychol* 21(1):61–72. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jevp.2000.0182>
- Delgado-Baquerizo M, Maestre FT, Reich PB, Jeffries TC, Gaitan JJ, Encinar D, Berdugo M, Campbell CD, Singh BK (2016) Microbial diversity drives multifunctionality in terrestrial ecosystems. *Nat Commun* 7:10541 <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10541>
- DeLucio JV, Múgica M (1994) Landscape preferences and behaviour of visitors to Spanish national parks. *Landsc Urban Plan* 29(2):145–160. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-2046\(94\)90024-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-2046(94)90024-8)
- Dominguez Lara SA (2014) ¿Matrices Policóricas/Tetracóricas o Matrices Pearson? Un estudio metodológico. *Rev Argent Cienc Comport* 6(1):39–48
- Esteve-Selma MA, Martínez-Fernández J, Hernández I, Montávez JP, López JJ, Calvo JF, Robledano F (2010) Effects of climatic change on the distribution and conservation of Mediterranean forests: The case of *Tetraclinis articulata* in the Iberian Peninsula. *Biodivers Conserv* 19(13):3809–3825. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-010-9928-4>
- Esteve-Selma MA, Martínez-Fernández J, Hernández-García I, Montávez JP, López-Hernández JJ, Calvo JF (2012) Potential effects of climatic change on the distribution of *Tetraclinis articulata*, an endemic tree from arid Mediterranean ecosystems. *Clim Change* 113(3–4):663–678. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-011-0378-0>
- Falk JH, Balling JD (2010) Evolutionary influence on human landscape preference. *Environ Behav* 42(4):479–493. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916509341244>
- Ferrando PJ, Anguiano-Carrasco C (2010) El análisis factorial como técnica de investigación en psicología. *Papel Psicol* 31(1):18–33

- Ferrando PJ, Demestre J, Anguiano-Carrasco C, Chico E (2011) Evaluación TRI de la escala I-E de Rotter: un nuevo enfoque y algunas consideraciones. *Psicothema* 23(2):282–288
- Ferrando PJ, Lorenzo-Seva U (2017) Program FACTOR at 10: Origins, development and future directions. *Psicothema* 29(2):236–240. <https://doi.org/10.7334/psicothema2016.304>
- Fishbein M, Ajzen I (1975) *Belief, attitude, intention and behavior: an introduction to Theory and Research*. Addison-Wesley, Reading, Massachusetts
- Folke C, Polasky S, Rockström J, Galaz V, Westley F, Lamont M, Scheffer M, Österblom H, Carpenter SR, Chapin FS, Seto KC, Weber EU, Crona BI, Daily GC, Dasgupta P, Gaffney O, Gordon LJ, Hoff H, Levin SA, ... Walker BH (2021) Our future in the Anthropocene biosphere. *Ambio* 50(4):834–869. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-021-01544-8>
- Forero CG, Maydeu-Olivares A, Gallardo-Pujol D (2009) Factor analysis with ordinal indicators: A monte Carlo study comparing DWLS and ULS estimation. *Struct Equ Modeling* 16(4):625–641. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705510903203573>
- Freiberg Hoffmann A, Stover JB, de la Iglesia G, Fernández Liporace M (2013) Correlaciones policóricas y tetracóricas en estudios factoriales exploratorios y confirmatorios. *Ciencias Psicológicas* 7:151–164. <https://doi.org/10.22235/cp.v7i1.1057>
- Frias-Navarro D (2021) *Research design, analysis and writing of results*. Valencia. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/KNGTP>
- García-Llorente M, Martín-López B, Iniesta-Arandia I, López-Santiago CA, Aguilera PA, Montes C (2012) The role of multi-functionality in social preferences toward semi-arid rural landscapes: An ecosystem service approach. *Environ Sci Policy* 19–20:136–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.01.006>
- Garland G, Banerjee S, Edlinger A, Miranda Oliveira E, Herzog C, Wittwer R, Philippot L, Maestre FT, van der Heijden MGA (2020) A closer look at the functions behind ecosystem multifunctionality: A review. *J Ecol* 109(2):600–613. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.13511>
- George D, Mallery M (2003) *Using SPSS for Windows step by step: a simple guide and reference*. Allyn & Bacon, Boston, Massachusetts
- Gifford R, Nilsson A (2014) Personal and social factors that influence pro-environmental concern and behaviour: A review. *Int J Psychol* 49(3):141–157. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.12034>
- Gil de Araujo Z (2019) *Educación ambiental y valoración del paisaje estepario en las comarcas del Valle del Ebro*. Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Madrid
- Gil Olcina A (2009) Clima e hipótesis de cambio climático en la región geográfica del sureste ibérico. *Investig Geogr-Spain* 49:5. <https://doi.org/10.14198/INGEO2009.49.01>
- Gómez-Benito J, Hidalgo MD (2010) El sesgo de los instrumentos de medición. *Papel Psicol* 31(1):75–84

- Hagerhall CM (2000) Clustering predictors of landscape preference in the traditional Swedish cultural landscape: Prospect-refuge, mystery, age and management. *J Environ Psychol* 20(1):83–90. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jevp.1999.0150>
- Hagerhall CM (2001) Consensus in landscape preference judgements. *J Environ Psychol* 21(1):83–92. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jevp.2000.0186>
- Hair JF, Black WC, Babin BJ, Anderson RE (2014) *Multivariate Data Analysis*. Pearson, 7ª Edición, Harlow, United Kingdom
- Hines JM, Hungerford HR, Tomera AN (1987) Analysis and Synthesis of Research on Responsible Environmental Behavior: A Meta-Analysis. *J Environ Educ* 18(2):1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.1987.9943482>
- Holland PW, Thayer DT (1986) Differential Item Performance and the Mantel-Haenszel Procedure. American Educational Research Association Annual Meeting, San Francisco, California
- Insko CA, Schopler J (1980) *Psicología social experimental. Texto con lecturas ilustrativas*. Ed. Trillas, Mexico
- Ives CD, Kendal D (2013) Values and attitudes of the urban public towards peri-urban agricultural land. *Land Use Policy* 34:80–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2013.02.003>
- Joye Y, Van den Berg A (2011) Is love for green in our genes? A critical analysis of evolutionary assumptions in restorative environments research. *Urban For Urban Green* 10(4):261–268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.140196>
- Jung S (2013) Exploratory factor analysis with small sample sizes: A comparison of three approaches. *Behav Processes* 97:90–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.beproc.2012.11.016>
- Kalivoda O, Vojar J, Skřivanová Z, Zahradník D (2014) Consensus in landscape preference judgments: The effects of landscape visual aesthetic quality and respondents' characteristics. *J Environ Manage* 137:36–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2014.02.009>
- Kaplan R, Kaplan S (1989) *The Experience of Nature; a Psychological Perspective*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
- Kaplan RM, Saccuzzo DP (2018) *Psychological Testing: Principles, Applications, and Issues*. Cengage Learning, Boston, Massachusetts
- Kiley HM, Ainsworth GB, van Dongen WFD, Weston MA (2017) Variation in public perceptions and attitudes towards terrestrial ecosystems. *Sci Total Environ* 590-591:440–451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.12.179>
- Kimura R, Moriyama M (2019) Recent Trends of Annual Aridity Indices and Classification of Arid Regions with Satellite-Based Aridity Indices. *Remote Sensing in Earth Systems Sciences* 2(2-3):88–95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41976-019-00014-w>
- López-de-Haro F, Fernández Martínez J, Cruz Asenjo Gómez M, Fernández Ortega F, Serrano Virgíl V, Martínez-Hernández F, Mota Poveda JF (2011). El conocimiento de la flora y su influencia en la valoración de los paisajes semiáridos andaluces y

en las actitudes hacia su conservación. V Congreso Biología de la Conservación de Plantas – Es Mercadal (Menorca)

- López-de-Haro F, Segura JA (2013) Los itinerarios didácticos: Un recurso interdisciplinar y vertebrador del curriculum. *Espiral. Cuadernos Del Profesorado* 6(12): Art. 12
- Louzán Mariño R (2020) Mejorar la calidad de las evaluaciones de riesgos psicosociales mediante el control de sesgos. *Archivos de Prevención de Riesgos Laborales* 23(1):68–81. <https://doi.org/10.12961/aprl.2020.23.01.06>
- Maestre FT, Quero JL, Gotelli NJ et al (2012) Plant Species Richness and Ecosystem Multifunctionality in Global Drylands. *Science* 335(6065):214–218. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1215442>
- Margules C, Usher MB (1981) Criteria used in assessing wildlife conservation potential: A review. *Biol Conserv* 21(2):79–109. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207\(81\)90073-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207(81)90073-2)
- Martínez-Hernández F, Medina-Cazorla JM, Mendoza-Fernández A, Pérez-García FJ, Sánchez-Gómez P, Garrido-Becerra JA, Gil C, Mota JF (2009) Preliminary essay on the chorology of the Iberian gypsumicolous flora: Rarity and richness of the gypsum outcrops. *Acta Bot Gall* 156(1):9–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/12538078.2009.10516138>
- Martínez-Hernández F, Pérez-García FJ, Garrido-Becerra JA, Mendoza-Fernández AJ, Medina-Cazorla JM, Martínez-Nieto MI, Calvente MEM, Poveda JFM (2011) The distribution of Iberian gypsophilous flora as a criterion for conservation policy. *Biodivers Conserv* 20(6):1353–1364. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-011-0031-2>
- Mendoza-Fernández A, Pérez-García FJ, Martínez-Hernández F, Medina-Cazorla JM, Garrido-Becerra JA, Merlo Calvente ME, Guirado Romero JS, Mota JF (2014) Threatened plants of arid ecosystems in the Mediterranean Basin: A case study of the south-eastern Iberian Peninsula. *Oryx* 48(4):548–554. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605313000495>
- McNeely JA (2003) Biodiversity in arid regions: Values and perceptions. *J Arid Environ* 54(1):61–70. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jare.2001.0890>
- Moreno M, Corraliza JA, Ruiz JP (2005) Escala de actitudes ambientales hacia problemas específicos. *Psicothema* 17(3):502–508
- Mota J, Cabello J, Cerrillo MI, Rodríguez-Tamayo ML (eds) (2004) *Los Subdesiertos de Almería: naturaleza de cine*. Consejería de Medio Ambiente, Junta de Andalucía, Spain
- Mota JF, Peñas J, Castro H, Cabello J, Guirado JS (1996) Agricultural development vs biodiversity conservation: the Mediterranean semiarid vegetation in El Ejido (Almería, southeastern Spain). *Biodivers Conserv* 5:1597–1617. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00052118>
- Ntuli H, Jagers SC, Linell A, Sjöstedt M, Muchapondwa E (2019) Factors influencing local communities' perceptions towards conservation of transboundary wildlife resources: The case of the Great Limpopo Trans-frontier Conservation Area.

Biodivers Conserv 28(11):2977–3003. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-019-01809-5>

- Orians GH (1980) Habitat selection: general theory and applications to human behavior. In: Lockard J (ed) *The evolution of human social behavior*, 1 ed. Elsevier, Chicago, pp 49-66
- Palmer JF, Hoffman RE (2001) Rating reliability and representation validity in scenic landscape assessments. *Landsc Urban Plan* 54:149–161. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2046\(01\)00133-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2046(01)00133-5)
- Pérez E, Medrano L (2010) Análisis factorial exploratorio: Bases conceptuales y metodológicas. *Rev Argent Cienc Comport* 2(1):58–66
- Pérez E, Medrano L, Sánchez Rosas J (2013) El Path Analysis: Conceptos básicos y ejemplos de aplicación. *Rev Argent Cienc Comport* 5:52–66
- Prieto G, Delgado AR (2010) Fiabilidad y validez. *Papel Psicol* 31(1):67–74
- Quiles MN, Marichal García F, Betancort V (1998) Las actitudes sociales. In: Quiles MN (ed) *Psicología social: Procesos interpersonales*. Pirámide, Madrid, pp 131-159
- Sahraoui Y, Clauzel C, Foltête J-C (2016) Spatial modelling of landscape aesthetic potential in urban-rural fringes. *J Environ Manage* 181:623–636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2016.06.031>
- Scott MJ, Canter DV (1997) Picture or place? A multiple sorting study of landscape. *J Environ Psychol* 17:263–281. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jevp.1997.0068>
- Shuttleworth S (1980) The use of photographs as an environmental presentation medium in landscape studies. *J Environ Manage* 11:61–76
- Steg L, Vlek C (2009) Encouraging pro-environmental behaviour: An integrative review and research agenda. *J Environ Psychol* 29(3):309–317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2008.10.004>
- Stewart TR, Middleton P, Downton M, Ely D (1984) Judgments of photographs vs. Field observations in studies of perception and judgment of the visual environment. *J Environ Psychol* 4(4):283–302. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-4944\(84\)80001-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-4944(84)80001-8)
- Tieskens KF, Van Zanten BT, Schulp CJE, Verburg PH (2018) Aesthetic appreciation of the cultural landscape through social media: An analysis of revealed preference in the Dutch river landscape. *Landsc Urban Plan* 177:128–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2018.05.002>
- Timmerman ME, Lorenzo-Seva U (2011) Dimensionality assessment of ordered polytomous items with parallel analysis. *Psychol Methods* 16(2):209–220. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0023353>
- Tveit MS (2009) Indicators of visual scale as predictors of landscape preference; a comparison between groups. *J Environ Manage* 90(9):2882–2888. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2007.12.021>
- Ulrich RS (1981) Natural Versus Urban Scenes: Some Psychophysiological Effects. *Environ Behav* 13(5):523–556. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916581135001>

- Valle Tendero F (2004). Modelos de Restauración Forestal: Datos botánicos aplicados a la gestión del Medio Natural Andaluz II: Series de vegetación. Consejería de Medio Ambiente de la Junta de Andalucía, Sevilla
- Vallejo PM, Sanz BU, Blanco ÁB (2003) Construcción de escalas de actitudes tipo Likert: Una guía práctica. La Muralla, Madrid
- Ventura-León JL, Caycho-Rodríguez T (2017) El coeficiente Omega: un método alternativo para la estimación de la confiabilidad. Revista Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Niñez y Juventud 15(1):625–627
- White RP, Nackoney J (2003) Drylands, people, and ecosystem goods and services: a *web-based geospatial analysis*. World Resources Institute, Washington, DC
- Wilson EO (1984) *Biofilia*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.